

THE RELEVANCE OF METAL CASTING AND ITS ROLE IN NIGERIA'S INDUSTRIALIZATION

Enang, Uwemedimo Patrick

Department of Industrial Technology Education

University of Uyo, Uyo.

08063320065

oodlifo4akaneno@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper examines the relevance of metal casting and its role in the industrial development of Nigeria. The industrial development of Nigeria revolves around the use of machines to produce, do jobs, and render Services than doing it manually Casting of metals are the end product produced by the foundry industries. Metal casting are used in a variety of industries which directly affect the industries and the end users of the cast products, such industries Include, automotive, medical prototypes, aerospace applications, electronics, defense, hardware, household, art and plant machinery. It is of great importance to the development of Nigeria's industrial sector, because it can be used to produce shapes, large pieces and parts with internal cavities to feed the needs of the country. Casting can produce very complex geometry and intricate shapes which could not be produce by machining or with other manufacturing processes. Ferrous and non ferrous metal materials could be cast and used to make small to very large size parts. Through casting tighter dimensional tolerances can be achieved because they are poured into a mold.

Keywords: Metal Casting, Relevance, Industrialization.

Introduction

Casting is a manufacturing process, which a liquid metal is poured into a mold which contains a hollow cavity of the desired shape and then allowed to solidify. It is a process that Involves pouring molten metal into a mold, allowing the metal to cool land solidify, then roving the part from the mold. According to the 2019 metal casting industry forecast and Trends report published by the American Foundry Society (AFS), US metal casting industry sales reached 33.1 billion dollars in 2018, a 10% Increase over 2017 (American Foundry Society, 2019). It is also worthwhile to mention that 90 percent of all manufactured goods and machinery have casting applications. This indicates that the rich and varied uses of metal casting has made it an invaluable manufacturing method for many Industries in Nigeria and the world at large. Metal casting is a process of pouring molten metal into a mold, which is a negative impression (of female replica) of the desired casting shape. As the liquid metal cools, it forms to the shape of the mold. Once solid, the casing is removed from the mold for further processing (Sahoo, *et al.*, 2014). It is a manufacturing process used to produce solid metal pieces called casting. It is a modem process with ancient roots, which has been widely used for sculpture especially in bronze, jewelry in precious metals weapons and tools.

Metal casting is adaptable to intricate shapes, to extremely large pieces and to mass

production; it produces parts with uniform physical and mechanical properties, depending on what is produced, its economic advantages can surpass other processes. Casting is normally performed in a foundry and the workers are referred to as foundry men. The casting process is essential to the development of any nation, as various object, shapes and sizes which cannot be machined, are produced by casting.

Metal Casting Technology

Metal casting dates back to 7,000 years ago. It is a process used in both manufacturing and fine art. During metal casting, the molten metal is transferred from crucible into a mold. A crucible is a ceramic or metal container in which metals or other substances may be melted or subjected to very high temperatures, it can also be made from any material that withstands very high temperature, a mold is a cavity in a material that receives the liquid metal and produce a cooled object in the shape of that cavity.

Mold Making, Cores And Gating System

A. Mold Making:

The mold is a negative space in which the molten metal will be poured, which must be created with precision and accuracy. Some molds are temporal while others are permanent and can be reused over and over. The type of mold chosen is based on the requirement of the final product. They include:

i. Sand Mold: It is made by compacting a mixture of sand and binding agent around a pattern, then removing the pattern and pouring molten metal into a created cavity. Sand molds are inexpensive and not as accurate as other types of mold. Sand molds are produced by creating the pattern or replica of the part, placing it in a mold flask, compacting the sand mixture around it to harden and cure.

The sand mold is supported by a mold flask and can be hardened through drying or baking.

ii. Shell Mold: This utilizes a mixture of resin-coated sand, known as shell sand, to create a thin, rigid shell around a pattern, until the desired shell thickness is achieved. The shell sand is heated and cured, often in a dedicated shell core machine. Shell molds are used for high - volume production, complex parts and tight tolerance.

iii. Investment Mold: Investment mold is also known as lost-wax mold. It is created using a wax pattern. The pattern is coated in a refractory material, such as ceramic slurry or plaster, which hardens to form the mold. Once the mold is dry, it is heated to melt and remove the wax, leaving behind a cavity. Investment molds are primarily used in precision casting for intricate and detailed parts.

iv. Permanent Mold: Also called gravity molds or die casting molds, are usually made of steel or other durable materials. They are designed for repetitive use and can withstand high temperatures and pressures. They are usually machined or fabricated, ensuring they are precise and durable enough for repeated use in the casting process (Campbell, 20Th).

B. CORES:

Cores refer to the internal structures that are used to create hollow spaces, cavities or complex geometries within a casting, they are usually made of sand or metal and placed in the mold cavity prior to casting. They are used to form internal passages, holes, recesses and other features that cannot be achieved by using only the mold. Cores can be solid or hollow.

Solid cores are used to form simple holes or recesses, while hollow cores create complex internal cavities. They are formed using core boxes, which is filled with the core material and compacted to achieve the desired shape. The core is then removed and placed in the mold cavity carefully to shape the internal features of the casting, and are often supported, gated and vented to ensure proper hung and solidification.

C. Gating Systems:

These refer to the network of channels and passages that are designed to control the flow of molten metal into a mold cavity. The primary purpose is to ensure proper filling of the mold, promote solidification of the casting and minimize defects like porosity and shrinkage. There are several types of gating systems used in foundry and casting processes, these include:

1. **Pouring Basin:** This is the initial reservoir, where molten metal is poured, before it flows into the mold.
2. **Sprue:** A sprue is a vertical passage that connects the pouring cup to the pattern and allow the molten metal to enter the mold.
3. **Runners:** These are channels that distribute the molten metal from the sprue to the various parts of the mold cavity. They may branch out into multiple runners to ensure even distribution of the metal.
4. **Gate:** A gate is a passage that connects the riser to the mold cavity. It allows the molten metal to enter the mold and flow through the inner system, preventing rapid flow and turbulence that may cause defects.
5. **Riser:** A riser is a reservoir of molten metal, used to feed the molten metal into the mold as it shrinks during solidification, it is also known as feed head.

D. Metal Melting And Pouring

Metal melting is the process of putting the raw materials which may be in form of scraps, ingots or billets, into a furnace for heating, to convert it from solid to molten state. The furnace can be electric, gas or induction type. Materials needed for metal melting are:

- i. **Furnace:** It can be electric, gas or induction type. It is a thermal enclosure for heating materials to suitable temperatures. The commonly used furnace for foundry smelting is the CUPOLA Furnace, however smaller furnaces may be used in school workshops.

- ii. The metal to be melted, which can be in form of scrap, ingots or billets.
- iii. An Insulating Material: Used to line the furnace to prevent heat loss.
- iv. A Crucible: Is a ceramic or metal container that holds the molten metal.
- v. An Extractor System: Is used to remove impurities from the molten metal.
- vi. A Ladle: Is a large deep spoon used for scooping and transferring molten metal from the furnace to the mold, it has a long handle that keeps the user's hand away from the heat of the molten metal. It is designed to prevent loss of heat from the metal, which could cause it to solidify before being poured into a mold. Some ladles have a built in pour spout, end may be made from steel, ceramics or cast iron.

Metal pouring on the other hand is a process which involves transferring molten metal from the furnace into the mold, which is done using a ladle. The molten metal is poured

into a mold through a spot on the ladle. If the ladle is large and much metal is to be poured, to fill the mold then the mold should be set on the floor and one or more helpers should be engaged to help In pouring the metal. If the ladle is small the mold may be set on the bench. The melted metal should be poured in a steady siren it must be poured in such a way that the gate and the sprue are kept full until the mold is filled. Thin casting must be poured faster than thick ones.

The desired composition of metals to be poured are achieved by adding alloys such as Zinc, Tin, Lead, Copper; and Aluminum. Molten metal should not be poured until is thoroughly melted. The metal should be heated until a layer of impurities forms on the top, called scum, which should be scooped off before pouring. Each of the alloy met ale added is based on the quality of the casting required.

Examples of alloy metals and their functions include:

Tin: To Improve fluidity of molten metals.

Zinc: To Improve strength and hardness of the casting.

Lead: To Improve fluidity and machinability of casting.

Copper: To improve strength and hardness of casting.

Aluminum: To improve strength of the casting and to reduce the weight of the finished product.

E. Casting Finishing Processes:

Casting finishing processes are a group of techniques used to improve the surface quality of cast parts. These processes can be used to remove surface defects and prepare the part for further processing or finishing. The complete process of finishing involves the removal of cores, gales and risers, cleaning of the casting surface and chipping of any unnecessary projections on the surface those processes include:

1. Cleaning
2. Short blasting
3. Vibratory finishing
4. Tumbling
5. Polishing

Each of these processes has its own advantages and disadvantages, and the best process to use will depend on the type of casting, the desired surface finish, size or shape of casting. Casting finishing processes are an important part of the manufacturing process and can have a significant impact on the final quality of the part produced.

(i) **Cleaning:** This is clone to remove any contaminants that may be present on the surface of the casting. These contaminants can include; molding sand, oxide sand, oxide scale and tool marks. Cleaning can be typically done using a combination of water and abrasives, such as sand or grit, in some cases, chemical cleaning agents may be used. The goal of cleaning is to prepare the casting for any additional finishing processes, without proper clearing other processes as shot blasting or polishing may not be effective.

(ii) **Short Biasing:** This method uses nil steel balls, called shots to clean and polish the

surface of the part. The shots are propelled at high speeds by compressed air or a steam of water and they impact the surface of the part. It could be used to prepare the surface of the part for subsequent finishing processes, such as painting.

(iii) **Vibratory finishing:** This process uses a vibrating machine to polish and debar castings. The machine consists of a bowl or tub filled with abrasive media, such as ceramic or plastic beads, and the casting is placed inside. The machine vibrates, causing the media to impact the surface of the casting and remove any rough areas. The vibratory motion also helps to distribute the media evenly around the casting, ensuring that all surfaces are finished evenly. It is often used on castings with smooth surfaces, as it can create a mirror-like uniform finish.

(v) **Tumbling:** This is a casting finishing process that uses a rotating drum filled with abrasive media to smoothen and polish the surface of the casting. The drum is filled with media, such as, sand, ceramic beads, or plastic pellets, and the casting is placed inside. The drum that rotates at a high speed, causing the media to impact the surface of the casting and remove any rough or irregular areas. It is used on casting with a simple shape, it is not as effective at reaching intricate details as some other finishing processes.

(v) **Polishing:** This is a finishing that uses abrasive materials, such as sand paper or buffing wheels, to create a smooth, shiny surface on the casting. The type of abrasive material used and the amount of pressure applied will determine the level of polish achieved. It is used on castings with smooth surfaces. That require a high quality finish such as decorative pieces or pieces that are used in the food or medical industries. Polishing can also be used to restore the original finish of a casting that has become dull or damaged overtime.

Metal Casting Processes

The metal casting process may be divided into two groups namely: hot forming and cold processes. Hot forming includes centrifugal casting, extrusion, forging, full mold casting, investment casting, permanent mold casting, plaster mold casting, sand casting, shell mold casting and metallurgy.

Cold processes on the other hand includes cold rolling, squeeze casting, pressure die casting, gravity die casting, burnishing process, coining process, cold forging, hobbling process, impact extrusion, preening process, sizing and thread rolling.

The hot forming process uses the oven, which is heated to a very high temperature of about 2000 degrees, while in the cold forming process a piece of metal is mildly heated, around room temperature.

The industrialization of any nation depends to a large extent on the effective use of the metal foundry industries. Industrialized nations of the world have sophisticated foundry industries which help them build different machines used in mass production of a wide variety of goods and improved services. For there to be a revolution industrially in the foundry and casting sector, Nigeria needs an automated process of casting metals, which helps in building different machines, and components, needed in the industrial sector. Production demands that casting be made much faster than hand operation permit.

High production foundries and some jobbing foundries use machine molding, core making and cleaning, whenever possible. Automate and semi-automate equipment in modern foundries produces at high production rates, and hand operation should be minimized as much as possible. The foundry industry is a manufacturing facility that specializes in product

castings using different processes while castings are free and product coated by fountains.

The foundry industry is built on man's ability to use methods, materials and machines to produce useful products from one of the earth's greatest natural resources metal, to accomplish this, practically, every occupational activity is represented. Considering the relevance of metal casting to the industrial development of the nation, the foundry industries needs willing and trained personnel with automated machines. It is an industry with a fascinated past, a booming present and brilliant future.

G. Casting Defects: Types, Causes And Prevention

Casting is prone to defects that can compromise its quality and performance. Casting defects are irregularities or imperfections that occur during the casting process, which can negatively impact the quality, properties and performance of the resulting cast components. These defects can rise from many factors which include;

Poor mold design, improper metal composition, incorrect pouring temperature, inadequate gating and risering.

Common casting defects include:

- (i) Porosity: This is the presence of pores or voids within the casting.
- (ii) Shrinkage: These are cavities or depressions in the casting due to solidification shrinkage.
- (iii) Inclusions: This is the presence of foreign particles or impurities within the casting.
- (iv) Cracks: These are fractures or separations in the casting materials.
- (v) Misalignment and Shifting: This is where the mold sections are not properly aligned, causing irregularities in the casting.

Causes of Casting Defects

Casting defects can be attributed to:

- (i) Poor Mold Design: Inappropriate mold design can lead to insufficient feeding of molten metal causing shrinkage defects (Campbell, 2011).
- (ii) Inadequate Gating and Risering: Improper placement or sizing of gates and risers can result in insufficient feeding, leading to defects (Dalton, 2012).
- (iii) Improper Metal Composition and Temperature: Incorrect alloy composition or pouring temperature can result in defects such as porosity and hot tear mg (Kurz & Fisher, 1984).
- (iv) **Mold Material and Quality:** Poor quality or unsuitable mold materials can introduce inclusion and cause defects, (Wanq et al., 2019).

Prevention of Casting Defects

The following measures can be implemented to prevent casting defects;

(i) Optimized Mold Design:

Proper mold design can ensure adequate feeding of molten metal during solidification, reducing shrinkage defects (Campbell, 2011).

(iii) **Adequate Gating and Risering:** Proper placement and sizing of gates and risers can help prevent shrinkage defects (Dalton, 2012).

(iii) **Proper Metal Composition and Temperature Control:** Maintaining correct alloy composition and pouring temperature can reduce defects such as porosity and hot tearing (Kurz and Fisher, 1984).

(iv) **High Quality Mold Materials and Processes:** Using Suitable mold materials and implementation of proper molding processes can minimize the occurrence of inclusions and other defects (Wang *et al.* 2019).

H. Safety Precautions During Casting:

Casting and foundry operations involve various hazards, including exposure to extreme temperatures molten metal, dust and noise. Safety precautions are essential to minimize risks and ensure a safe working environment, they include:

i) **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):** Workers should wear appropriate Personal Protective Equipment, including heat resistant gloves, protective clothing, safety glasses, face shields and sturdy footwear (OSHA, 2018).

(ii) **Training and Education:** All workers should receive proper safety training, including hazard identification, safe work practices and emergency procedures (NIOSH, 2017).

(iii) **Temperature Control and Monitoring Temperature** monitoring devices should be used to ensure that molten metal is maintained at safe temperatures (NIOSH, 2017).

(iv) **Machine Guarding:** All machines should be equipped with appropriate safety guards to protect workers from moving parts and flying debris, and other hazards (OSHA, 2018).

(v) **Ventilation and Dust Control:** Proper ventilation systems should be in place to control airborne dust and fumes. Workers should also wear respirators when necessary (OSHA, 2018).

(vi) **Noise Control Hearing protection** should be worn in noisy areas, and engineering controls should be implemented to reduce noise levels (NIOSH, 2017).

(vii) **Material Handling and Storage:** Safe handling and storage practices should be implemented for raw materials, molten metal, and finished casting to minimize the risk of accident (OSHA 2018).

(viii) **Housekeeping and Maintenance:** Good housekeeping practices, such as regular cleaning and maintenance should be maintained to ensure a safe working environment (NIOSH, 2017).

(ix) **Emergency Preparedness:** All workers should be trained in emergency response procedures, and appropriate emergency equipment, such as fire extinguishers and first aid kits, should be readily available (OSHA, 2018).

I. Relevance of Metal Casting in Industrial Development of Nigeria

The use of cast metals in the industrial development of Nigeria has several implications. Cast metals are essential materials in various industries, they play a vital role driving economic growth and development (Umanah, Willie, Daniel, 2024). They include steel, iron, and aluminum which can be used in various industries such as construction, automatic machinery etc and can contribute to Infrastructural development and advancement in technology (Abaikpa, Thomas and Udom, 2022).

The availability of cast metals In Nigeria can promote local industrialization and

reduce dependency on imported products. Cast materials are known for their strength, durability and versatility, making them suitable for a wide range of applications. Nigeria can enhance its manufacturing sector and reduce the need for costly imports, by developing a domestic production capability (Willie, Mboho and Udom, 2023), 'This can lead to job creation, economic development and income generation (Saviour, Udom and Clement, 2024). The availability of locally produced cast metals can support the construction of infrastructure projects, such as building, bridges, transportation networks etc, contributing to the overall development of the country (Daniel, Udousoro and Effiong, 2024).

The development of a good cast metal industry can attract foreign investment and promote international trade with other countries, while leading to the transfer of technology, knowledge sharing, and the creation of business opportunities, thus stimulating industrial growth and development in the country.

There are some challenges and considerations related to the use of cast metals in Nigeria's industrial sector. The need for an efficient supply chain of raw materials, availability of quality iron ore, coal and several other inputs needed for cast metal production are some of the considerations in the industry. Good investment in mining, extraction and processing facilities is needed to ensure a constant supply of raw materials, reducing dependence on imports.

The environmental impact of cast metal production should also be considered. In the process of casting metals, high energy is consumed and emitted. It is essential to implement sustainable practices, such as adopting cleaner and more efficient technology, using recycled materials and managing waste and emission properly to mitigate the environmental impact and ensure sustainable development. It is essential to address issues and challenges related to the raw materials supply chain and environmental impact to ensure sustainable and responsible development in the cast metal industry, thus drive local industrialization, reduce dependency on imported products, contribute to infrastructure development, attract foreign investment, promote international trade and income generation (Nana and Udom, 2023; Kingdom, Wisdom, Udom and Edidiong, 2024).

Conclusion

Metal casting consists of pouring or forcing molten metal into a mold cavity with the desired shape and allowing it for some time to solidify. Producing high quality casting could be very challenging in Nigeria, the sector is long standing and divided into ferrous casting and non-ferrous casting. The ferrous casting subsector includes; cast iron, and steel while the non-ferrous casting sub-sector include non ferrous metals like bronze, tin brass, copper aluminum and others. The metal casting Industry in Nigeria is broken into pieces, with a large number of small and medium sized enterprises. (SMEs. There is a lack of advanced technology in the industry and many of them operating have outdated machines which does not allow them to produce optimally. The industry is lucrative and need to be expanded.

Recommendations

1. The metal casting industry needs to stay competitive by focusing on research and new technologies which are constantly emerging to help develop the industry especially

those on the roadside.

2. Metal casting is a highly skilled profession as such resources should be invested in training the workers in the industry, to equip them with the required skills.
3. The industry should improve upon its impact on the environment in a bit to mitigate the effects of dangerous gases emitted into the environment during the process of casting, such gases are: Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂) Nitrogen Oxide (NO_y) and Carbon Monoxide (CO).
4. Metal casting is a technical field having a strong foundation in the technical and science subjects, it will be of great advantage if technical schools and trade schools are properly equipped for such trainings and in related subjects.
5. Government should fund and support registered foundry businesses to help them acquire standard equipment, for optimal production.

References

- American Foundry Society (2019). Metal Casting Industry Forecast and Times. Schaumburg, American Foundry Society. <https://castlngssa.com>. Oct. 5th 2024.
- Abaikpa Udeme Anthony, Thomas Cornelia David and Udom, Daniel, (2022). Open Innovation and Organizational Performance in Selected Firms in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *International Journal of Social Science Humanity & Management Research*. Volume 01 Issue 06 December 2022 Page No. 198-211.
- Abaikpa, Udeme Anthony, Thomas, Cornelia David, Udoh, Unwana Nicholas and Udom Sunday Daniel, (2023). Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Performance in Commercial Banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, Mar-2023 ISSN (2226-8235) Vol-12, Issue 3.
- Abaikpa, Udeme Anthony, Thomas, Cornelia David, Udom Sunday Daniel and Emmanuel, Okon Etuk (2023). Human Capital Management and Organizational Performance in United Bank for Africa Plc. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, Mar-2023 ISSN (2226-8235) Vol-12, Issue 3 <https://www.ijmsbr.com/> Page 33.
- Black, J. and Kohser, R. (2008). Degarmos materials and processes in manufacturing, John Willey and Sons, Inch, Hoboken, Now Jersey 10th edition).
- Campbell, J. (2011). Complete Casting Handbook Metal Casting Processes. Metallurgy, Techniques and Design. Oxford, UK: Elsevier.
- Campbell, J. (2015). Complete casting Handbook metal casting processes, metallurgy, techniques and design, Oxford, UK: Elsevier.
- Dalton, N. (2012). Casting and Remedies. Foundry Trade Journal. Retrieved from [https://www.ioundry-tradejoumaicom/en\)foundry-practice/casilnf-defects-and-re-medies.html](https://www.ioundry-tradejoumaicom/en)foundry-practice/casilnf-defects-and-re-medies.html). March 31st, 2024.
- Groover, M. P. (2012). Introduction to manufacturing processes. John Wiley & Sons. *In international Journal of Cast Metals Research. Science and Engineering of Cast Metal Solidification and Casting Processes*, 2023 volume 36(1).

- J. K Lad (2014). Casting Defect Causes, Seluhons and Prevention”. In: K H J. Busc how and T. T. Liu (Eds), *Handbook of Metals*, Elsevier B V. 1945-1962 p.
- Kalpakjlan, S. and Schmid, S. R. (2009). Manufacturing processes for engineering materials (6th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ, 195k Pearson Education.
- Khan, M. A. A., Sheik A. K., Gasem, Z. M. and Mad, M. (2022). Fatigue life and reliability of steel castings through integrated simulations and experiments. Based, Switzerland: Multi disciplinary Digital Publishing Institute.
- Kurz, W., and Fisher, D.J. (1g84). Fundamentals of Solidification. Aedermannsdorf, Switzerland: Transtech Publications.
- Nana, Aniekan Etim and Udom S. Daniel (2023). Harnessing Culture and Tourism for National Development; AKU; *An African Journal of Contemporary Research*. vol.4 No.4 2023. A publication of the Association for the promotion of African Studies.
- National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH). 201). Safety and Heal the Topics: Foundries Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdcgov/niosht/topics/foundries/safety-harzardshtml>. March 31st 2024.
- Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA). 2018. Safety and Health Topics Foundries Safety Hazards and Protective Measures. Occupational Safety and Health Administration. <https://www.osha.gov/SLTC//foundnes/safety-harzards.html> March 3111 2024.
- Oguntuyi, S. D., Nyantwe, K, Shongwe, M B. and Mojisola. T. (2023). Challenges and recent progress on the application of rapid sand casting for pan production: A review. *The International Journal of Advanced Technology* 128 (9), 47 41 4772.
- Prashant, P (2010). Introduction to manufacturing technologies. Principles and technologies, Mumbai, India: Jaico Publishing
- Sahoo, M. and Sabu, S. (2014). Principles of metal casting, third Edition, New York, N. Y: McGraw-Hill Education, 3rd edition. <https://workshopinsider.com/metal-casting-process>. 8th October, 2024.
- Saviour Sebastian Udo, Udom Sunday Daniel and Clement Etti Willie (2024). Public Administration Policies and Effects on Nigerian Economy. *AKSU Annals of Sustainable Development*, volume 2 Number 1; June 2024. ISSN: (P) 3027-0499: ISSN: (E) 3043-4955. <https://doi.org/10.60787/AASD-v2il-31>.
- Wang, H., Han, Q, Song, Y, and Liu, Y. (2019). Defects in Sand Castings: Causes and Remedies. Foundry, 1 -9, 31st March, 2024.
- Willie, Clement Etti, Daniel, Udom Sunday and Udousoro, Tahirih Emmanuel (2024). Proliferation of Media Houses and the Promotion of Local Contents and Employment Generation in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *AKSU Annals of Sustainable Development*, Volume 2, Number 1, June 2024; ISSN (P) 3027-0499; ISSN: (E) 3043-4955. <https://doi.org/10.60787/AASD-v2i1-39>

